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INVESTOR PREFERENCE FOR MUTUAL FUNDS POST ECONOMIC MELTDOWN

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ABSTRACT

The global interest and demand for mutual funds have increased dramatically as they provide an excellent opportunity to obtain a more diversified portfolio through professional services of fund managers. But an average retail investor has always lost with bearish trends post economic meltdown which began in 2008 and this has led to decrease in growth rate of assets under management of various mutual funds.

Understanding of factors affecting investor preference is critical to asset managers. This study aims to deepen current knowledge on investor behaviour by an analysis of individuals' investment decisions in mutual funds after an economic meltdown through a survey of mutual fund investors in India.

Two-group discriminant analysis was used to find out the factors important in differentiating between the two mutually exclusive categories of mutual fund investors formed for the study: (i) who remained invested in the mutual funds post economic meltdown and (ii) who stopped any further investment in mutual funds post meltdown. The independent discriminating variables taken were income of investor, percentage of income invested in mutual funds, age of investor, time perspective of investment, family size of investor, investor's attitude towards risk, past returns from mutual funds received by investor and information about investment avenues as well as general economic conditions.

The results revealed that income of investor, time perspective of investment, investor's attitude towards risk, past returns from mutual funds and information play a significant role in influencing the investment decision regarding mutual funds after economic meltdown.

Keywords: Mutual Funds, Investor preference, Discriminant analysis, Economic meltdown,

JEL Classification: D14, G11

1. INTRODUCTION

The mutual fund industry in India started in 1963 with the formation of Unit Trust of India, at the initiative of the Government of India and Reserve Bank of India. 1987 marked the entry of non-UTI, public sector mutual funds set up by public sector banks and Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) and General Insurance Corporation of India (GIC). SBI Mutual Fund was the first non-UTI Mutual Fund established in June 1987. At the end of 1993, the mutual fund industry had assets under management of Rs.47,004 crores. A new era started in the Indian mutual fund industry with the entry of private sector funds in 1993 giving the Indian investors a wider choice of investment avenues.

There are a lot of investment avenues available today in the financial market for an investor with an investable surplus. He can invest in Bank Deposits, Corporate Debentures and Bonds where there is low risk but low return or in capital market which has greater element of risk but has the potential to yield high returns. With falling interest rates on investments like Public Provident Fund (PPF), National Saving Certificate (NSC), bank deposits, etc., retail investors in India have been looking for the investment alternative he/she should adopt. Going with direct investment in capital market is an expensive proposal, and requires expert knowledge; and keeping money in the above mentioned saving instruments does not yield desirable return. Mutual funds offer the middle route to the retail investor for earning better return on investment with the help of professional management of funds.

The global interest and demand for mutual funds have increased dramatically during recent years. Mutual funds are today a very important savings vehicle for most people in developing countries and they provide an excellent opportunity to obtain a more diversified portfolio through investments in new markets and asset classes. Mutual funds have not only been an important savings vehicle in the past, they are also likely to gain importance since the reforms of current public pension systems tend to suggest a movement from defined benefit systems towards defined contribution systems. This implies providing individuals the opportunity to make their own investment decision through investments in mutual funds, which also results in high net inflows to the industry in the future.

But the volatile capital markets have left the investors in a fix, because the return on mutual fund investment will follow the bourses. The recent trends in the Stock Market have shown that an average retail investor always lost with periodic bearish trends. This has led to many investors opting out of capital markets and therefore also of mutual funds. This has led to

decrease in growth rate of assets under management of various mutual funds post economic meltdown which triggered in the year 2008.

In the light of the fast growth and the increasing importance of the mutual fund industry in the society, understanding of investor behaviour is critical to policymakers and asset managers to successfully meet the many challenges and opportunities. Policymakers need to have an understanding of investor behaviour in order to design the new defined contribution systems appropriately. Similarly, an understanding of investor behaviour is an important task for asset managers in order to be successful in the battle of fund flows. This study aims to deepen current knowledge on investor behaviour by a detailed examination of individuals' investment decisions in mutual funds after an economic meltdown.

2. EARLIER STUDIES

Several studies which examine investor behaviour have appeared in financial and economic literature. Many examine the relation between aggregate inflows of funds and fund characteristics, which provides interesting evidence on the investors' decision making. A significant body of research suggests that past risk-adjusted mutual fund performance helps predict future risk-adjusted performance (Elton and Gruber, 1989; Grinblatt and Titman, 1989). Consistent with these findings, there is some empirical evidence that mutual fund investors make purchase decisions on the basis of past performance (Kane et al., 1990; Patel et al., 1992). Sirri and Tufano (1998) show that there exists a strong positive relation between risk-adjusted returns and inflows to U.S. funds. Chevalier and Ellison (1997) show that the relation between inflows and past returns is convex, that is, the best performing funds become rewarded by the majority share of net inflows. Del Guercio and Tkac (2002) find that in contrast to mutual fund investors, pension clients punish poorly performing managers by withdrawing assets under management and do not flock disproportionately to recent winners. Wilcox (2003) also found that investors pay attention to past performance of mutual funds. Past return has been put forward as the most important determinant of mutual fund flows. However, other evidence suggests that investors use several factors other than return and risk such as amount of sales charge, management fees, fund manager reputation, fund family, clarity of the fund's accounting statement, etc. Findings suggest that investors are fee sensitive to some extent. Sirri and Tufano (1998) document a negative relation between fund fees and inflows. Moreover, Khorana and Servaes (2011) show that price-competition is an effective strategy in increasing a fund's market share, that is, funds that reduce their fees tend

to grow faster. Apart from these, Engström and Westerberg (2004) examine Swedish data and document somewhat different investor behaviour. Their results suggest that the management fee has a stronger impact on investors' behaviour than past returns, in that they avoid high-fee funds. Furthermore, they document evidence to suggest that indirect costs, due to unfamiliarity, matters when investor choose funds. For instance, given past performance and fee level, Sweden based funds receive higher inflow of capital than corresponding foreign fund manager. Barber and Odean (2004) find strong evidence that taxes matter for individual investors and investors prefer to locate bonds and mutual funds in retirement accounts. Vinod (2004) makes the choice between mutual funds realistic and rigorous by incorporating (i) unconventional non-expected utility theories implying four desirable properties of utility functions, and (ii) the fourth-order stochastic dominance. In their study of consumer rationality and the mutual fund purchase decision, Capon et al. (1996) explored the extent to which investors make purchase decisions consistent with modern finance theory i.e. on the basis of investor beliefs regarding the future return and risk of those assets (Elton and Gruber, 1989; Markowitz, 1959). Study results offered support for the notion that the mutual fund investment decision is better considered in a multi-attribute framework, where return and risk are merely two of a set of attributes the importance of which varies across investors.

Not many investor preference studies have been undertaken in India on a comprehensive scale especially to understand the change in investor preference for mutual funds after the global economic meltdown triggered in the year 2008. This study is proposed to fill this gap in the existing body of knowledge. The findings will be meaningful for mutual fund houses as well as policymakers to devise strategies for attracting investment into capital market via mutual funds when faced with economic crisis situations.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This study considers a multi-attribute framework in analyzing investor decisions regarding purchase of mutual funds post economic meltdown. The study was conducted between March 2014 and July 2015. Data were collected through an online survey of 273 investors with mutual fund investments at present or in the past 10 years. 734 surveys were sent out and 273 responses received (yielding a 37 per cent response rate). The mean subject age was 37.8 years (standard deviation = 10.4 years); 88 per cent were male, 12 per cent female; 87 per cent were married, 13 per cent widowed, divorced or single; 71 per cent were salaried and 29 per cent self employed.

The attributes providing most discriminatory power were confirmed through a two-group discriminant analysis. Two mutually exclusive categories of mutual fund investors were formed for the study: (i) who remained invested in the mutual funds post economic meltdown and (ii) who stopped any further investment in mutual funds post meltdown. The independent discriminating variables taken were income of investor, percentage of income invested in mutual funds, age of investor, time horizon of investment, family size of investor, investor's attitude towards risk, past returns from mutual funds received by investor and information about investment avenues as well as general economic conditions.

Question items used, in most cases, were adapted from prior literature using a 7-point Likert scale with anchors ranging from *strongly agree* to *strongly disagree*. When developing the questionnaire, content validity was established through careful selection and adaptation of items from previously validated instruments. After that, the questionnaire was pretested with 10 investors. The feedback from the pilot test was used to improve the readability and the quality of the questions in the instrument.

Variables

Annual income of the investor was taken and percentage of income invested annually in mutual funds was calculated according to their annual investments in mutual funds. Age in completed years was taken and constructs were developed for rest of the variables. Questions related to time horizon included selling intent due to daily fluctuations, quarterly losses if occurring due to market slump, focus on long term investment and time frame of requirement of money in future. Family size was asked along with the number of financially dependent members in the family. Questions related to Risk attitude included choice of high risk- high return mutual funds, uneasiness with losses in mutual funds investment, choice of investment in low risk mutual funds, choice of investment in traditional saving instruments like fixed deposits, National Saving Certificates, etc. and settling with medium returns with medium risk mutual funds. Information construct included questions related to awareness about the basic concept of mutual fund and its advantages, information about fund managers, type of mutual funds and fund management charges or load structure, understanding of the concept of averaging (in systematic investment plan) and compounding, information and understanding about general economic conditions such as inflation, GDP growth, tax policy, etc.

3. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Prior to data analysis, the research instrument was assessed for its reliability. Cronbach's coefficient alpha was computed to test for reliability of constructs. Table 1 shows the Cronbach's alpha for the constructs in the research framework. Nunnally (1967) suggested that a minimum alpha of 0.6 sufficed for early stages of research. As the Cronbach's alphas range from 0.64 to 0.91, the constructs are deemed to have adequate reliability for the next stage of analysis.

TABLE 1: Reliability Analysis

Construct	No. of items	Cronbach's alpha
Time Horizon	4	0.64
Family Size	2	0.91
Risk Attitude	4	0.82
Information	6	0.89

Table 2 gives the results of the test for equality of group means. Wilks' λ , sometimes also called the U statistic, for each predictor is the ratio of the within-group sum of squares to the total sum of squares. Its value varies between 0 and 1. Large values of λ (near 1) indicate that group means do not seem to be different. Small values of λ (near 0) indicate that the group means seem to be different. The results indicate that the group means for income, risk attitude, time perspective and information are significantly different at 1 percent level of significance while past returns are also significantly different but at 5 percent level of significance.

TABLE 2 : Tests of Equality of Group Means

Wilks' λ and univariate F ratio with 1 and 271 degrees of freedom

	Wilks' λ	F Ratio	Sig.
Income	.488	19.986	.000
Risk attitude	.582	17.908	.000
Time horizon	.316	23.798	.000
Family size	.776	3.167	.103
Age	.983	.188	.673
Percentage Income invested	.959	.474	.505
Information	.586	18.762	.000
Past returns	.670	5.415	.040

Table 3 gives the summary of canonical discriminant functions. Part (i) gives the eigenvalues and Wilk's λ . For each discriminant function, the Eigenvalue is the ratio of between-group to within-group sums of squares. Large Eigenvalues imply superior functions. The eigenvalue derived here is 13.760 and thus implies satisfactory discriminant function. Wilk's λ is 0.04 again indicating significant difference in groups based on the discriminant function (chi-square value significant).

Part (ii) of Table 3 gives the structure matrix or discriminant loadings. The strongest discriminator was the time perspective of investment. The attitude towards risk, information, past returns from mutual funds and income were moderate discriminators. Family size, percentage of income invested in mutual funds and age of the investor were not found to be significant discriminators.

92.3% of original grouped cases were correctly classified and 89.2% of cross-validated grouped cases were correctly classified.

TABLE 3: Summary of Canonical Discriminant Functions

(i) Eigenvalues and Wilks' λ

Function	Eigenvalue	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Canonical Correlation	Wilks' λ	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	13.760	100.0	100.0	.978	.044	21.875	8	.005

(ii) Structure Matrix (Discriminant Loadings)

Function 1

Time horizon	.315
Risk attitude	.182
Information	.180
Past returns	.150
Income	.144
Family size	-.115
Percentage of income invested in mutual funds	-.045
Age	-.028

Pooled within-groups correlations between discriminating variables and standardized canonical discriminant functions. Variables ordered by absolute size of correlation within function.

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study aims to deepen current knowledge on investor behaviour by an analysis of individuals' investment decisions in mutual funds after an economic meltdown through a survey of mutual fund investors. The results of the two-group discriminant analysis conducted for the purpose of this study suggest that the mutual fund investors who continued to invest in mutual funds post meltdown and the ones who completely stopped investing in mutual funds post economic meltdown can be discriminated on the basis of five discriminating variables of time perspective of investment, the attitude towards risk, information, past returns from mutual funds and income.

The strongest discriminator was time perspective of investment. Investors who have surplus funds to be kept invested in mutual funds for a longer time period are the ones who have continued to invest in mutual funds. This may be due to the fact that they are not expecting any liquidity crisis due to need of cash in the short run which may force them to redeem their mutual funds investment in a falling capital market.

Attitude towards risk is the second most important discriminator. Investors who are risk averse have stopped investing in mutual funds post economic meltdown as they consider the loss due to capital market risk too high for the difference in returns of mutual funds compared to risk free avenues like fixed or recurring deposits in the banks. Thus the risk return trade-off plays an important role in decisions regarding mutual fund investments post meltdown.

The third significant discriminator is information regarding various information avenues, concept and advantages of investing in mutual funds, types of mutual funds, fund managers, load structure of funds, concept of averaging through systematic investment plans and general economic conditions that may affect capital market returns. Investors who have more information on these issues are more likely to continue investing in mutual funds post meltdown as they understand the basic premises underlying mutual funds and are in a position to derive benefits of averaging, professional fund management and can make better choice of funds.

The fourth discriminator which was found significant is past returns from mutual funds. Investors who have received higher returns from mutual funds as compared to other investment avenues which are comparatively less risky or have not suffered significant losses in mutual funds have continued to invest in mutual funds post economic meltdown while those who have received minimal returns or have incurred losses are wary of investing in mutual funds now as they do not see any advantage of professional fund management during bear phases of the market.

The last significant discriminator is the income of the investor. Investors with comparatively lower incomes tend to withdraw from mutual funds post meltdown. This can be explained by utility theory as the utility of money invested is higher for a lower income investor than a high income investor and thus the disutility from loss of that money will be more in case of low income investor. Therefore investors with lower incomes are more inclined towards risk free investment avenues than mutual funds which involve an element of risk.

Family size, percentage of income invested in mutual funds and age of the investor were not found to be significant discriminators. This may be due to the fact that investors even though in the same age group, have different levels of income and responsibilities which determines their attitude towards risk and thus investment in mutual funds. Similarly, investors with same family size are in different stages of life and hence their time perspective of investment differs affecting their decisions regarding mutual fund investments. Percentage of income

invested in mutual funds did not vary much in the sample and this may have led to it not being a significant discriminator.

Information has come out to be an important discriminator in the study which suggests that mutual fund houses should try to create awareness about the various types of funds they are offering and also educate investors about the basic concepts of averaging and compounding so that the investors with lower incomes too start investing again in mutual funds through systematic investment plans. Apart from this, investors pay attention to past returns they have received from mutual funds in which they had invested pre-meltdown. Mutual fund advisors should try to educate the investors about the right selection of fund and long term investment which may restrict losses to some extent. Ethical practices should be followed by fund managers to bring back the confidence of retail investors in mutual funds. Fund managers must make use of their expertise during meltdowns especially now when short selling has been allowed for mutual funds in India as minimization of losses during such periods can help retain investors who remain invested if the past returns are above benchmark indices.

REFERENCES

- Barber, B. M., & Odean, T. 2000. Are Individual Investors Tax Savvy? Evidence from Retail and Discount Brokerage Accounts. *Journal of Public Economics*, 88(1), 419-442.
- Capon, N., Fitzsimons, G.J. and Prince, R.A. 1996. An Individual Level Analysis of The Mutual Fund Investment Decision, *Journal of Financial Services Research*, Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 59-82.
- Chevalier, J. and G. Ellison 1997. Risk Taking by Mutual Funds as a Response to Incentives, *Journal of Political Economy*, 105, 1167-1200.
- Cohn, R. A., Lewellen, W. G., Lease, R. C., & Schlarbaum, G. G. 2012. Individual Investor Risk Aversion and Investment Portfolio Composition. *The Journal of Finance*, 30(2), 605-620
- Del Guercio, D., & Tkac, P. A. 2002. The Determinants of The Flow of Funds of Managed Portfolios: Mutual Funds Vs. Pension Funds. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 37(4), 523-558.
- Edelen, R. M. 1999. Investor Flows and The Assessed Performance of Open-End Mutual Funds. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 53(3), 439-466.
- Elton, E.J., Gruber, M.J. 1989. *Modern Portfolio Theory and Empirical Work*, John Wiley and Sons, New York.
- Engström, S., & Westerberg, A. 2004. Information Costs and Mutual Fund Flows (No. 555). SSE/EFI Working paper series in Economics and Finance, Stockholm School of Economics.

- Grinblatt, M., Titman, S. 1989. Mutual Fund Performance: An Analysis of Quarterly Portfolio Holdings, *Journal of Business*, Vol. 62, pp.393-416.
- Hendricks, D., Patel, J., & Zeckhauser, R. 2012. Hot Hands in Mutual Funds: Short-Run Persistence of Relative Performance, 1974–1988. *The Journal of Finance*, 48(1), 93-130.
- Kane, A., Santini, D., & Aber, J. 1992. Lessons from the Growth History of Mutual Funds. Graduate School of International Relations and Pacific Studies, University of California.
- Khorana, A., & Servaes, H. 2011. What Drives Market Share in the Mutual Fund Industry?. *Review of Finance*, 16(1), 81-113.
- Markowitz, H. 1959, Portfolio Selection: Efficient Diversification of Investments, John Wiley and Sons, New York.
- Patel, J., Zeckhauser, R., & Hendricks, D. 1994. Investment flows and performance: Evidence from Mutual Funds, Cross-border Investments and New Issues. in Ryuzo Sato, Rama V. Ramachandran, Richard M. Levich ed. Japan, Europe and the International Financial Markets: Analytical and Empirical Perspectives, Cambridge University Press, 51-72.
- Sirri, E.R., and P. Tufano 1998. Costly Search and Mutual Fund Flows, *Journal of Finance*, 53, 1589-1622.
- Vinod, H. D. 2004. Ranking mutual funds using unconventional utility theory and stochastic dominance. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 11(3), 353-377.
- Wilcox, R. T. 2003. Bargain Hunting or Star Gazing? Investors' Preferences for Stock Mutual Funds. *The Journal of Business*, 76(4), 645-663.